

ESCALATING INTERVENTIONS TO IMPROVE BEHAVIOUR AND PERFORMANCE IN AN UNDERGRADUATE STATISTICS MODULE

Emma Howard¹, Maria Meehan¹ and Andrew Parnell²

¹University College Dublin and ²Maynooth University

In this study, we present the implementation of an early warning system in a large introductory statistics module which is escalated over four semester offerings. An early warning system identifies students who are at risk of failing or dropping out of a module, and provides them with supporting interventions. While familiar undergraduate mathematics supports include formative assessment and peer-assisted learning, our interventions tried to encourage student engagement through personalised emails which detailed supports and how students were progressing in the module. In later escalations, at-risk students received weekly emails encouraging them to use the Maths Support Centre. We believe our module-based interventions had limited impact upon the at-risk students. In hindsight, we believe these students needed programme-level interventions. Overall, this study provides insights for others into implementing learning analytics interventions.

INTRODUCTION

With the availability of data, learning analytics has become an international trend with positive implementations reported worldwide. Campbell and Oblinger (2007) consider the five steps in the analytics cycle to be: Capture; Report; Predict; Act; and, Refine. There is currently a wealth of papers on prediction models for learning analytics. However, research on the ‘Act’ and ‘Refine’ steps are not as prevalent with a limited amount of evidence-based studies available. Familiar supports in third-level mathematics modules may include formative feedback or peer-support. Recently learning analytics interventions have been implemented in STEM modules (Cai, Lewis, & Higdon, 2015).

Here, in our quasi-experimental study, we evaluate an escalating intervention provided to students in four offerings of a large undergraduate statistics module, *Practical Statistics*. In the first two offerings of the module, a feedback email was sent to all students containing study advice and details allowing them to compare their continuous assessment at that time to that of their peers. On finding no positive benefit of the intervention, in subsequent offerings of the module, the intervention was escalated. In the third offering, students were provided with their predicted final module mark in the feedback email, and at-risk students were targeted with weekly emails from the manager of the university Maths Support Centre (MSC). In addition to these escalations, the fourth offering catered for a face-to-face meeting between each at-risk student and their lecturer, an author of this paper. We measure the effectiveness of these supports by examining changes in behaviour and performance. To do this, we analyse Learning Management System (LMS) data, academic marks, and MSC attendance data from six offerings of the module ($N = 876$). The six offerings include four offerings where an intervention occurred and two offerings which were used for comparison purposes in the statistical analysis. Whilst some hypothesis tests of our interventions were statistically

significant, we believe that these were not of practical significance for the students. However, we argue that our study shows how an intervention may be refined and affirms the need to focus on how to evaluate the impact of interventions.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A popular learning analytics intervention is an early warning system. This consists of identifying students at risk of failing or dropping out and providing them with support (an intervention). The identification of at-risk students is commonly performed through prediction modelling, although some universities have dedicated support staff to identify them (based on students' GPA, whether they are repeating, inconsistent grades et cetera). There have been a number of studies that investigate how to develop accurate prediction models for early warning systems, including in engineering and mathematics modules (Corrigan, Smeaton, Glynn, & Smyth, 2015). For this study, we focus on the intervention and the evaluation of its effectiveness. Dawson, Jovanovic, Gašević and Pardo (2017) assert that a limited number of studies provide examples of applying and measuring the effectiveness of interventions.

We focus on module-level interventions where students are identified as at-risk and are provided with an intervention based on their progress in a single module. Choi, Lam, Li, and Wong (2018) suggest an intervention strategy should encourage a good student-lecturer relationship (starting with a welcome email), and involve ranking of students by their prediction results with a proactive strategy that initially focuses on students at high risk of failing and which shifts to low-risk students in the final stages of the module. Na and Tasir (2017) conducted a systematic review of learning analytics interventions specifically in online learning, and found that the interventions implemented could be classified as: providing additional, or substantially changing, teaching materials; emailing students; providing advice to students; posting of a signal to a student dashboard; arranging a face-to-face meeting; improving module materials; and, texting students. Na and Tasir (2017) note that no study used tutoring as an intervention. However, they hypothesise that this may be owing to challenges faced by the organisation and implementation of tutoring in online learning.

Cai et al. (2015) piloted an intervention scheme in an intermediate algebra module. This included a dashboard which allowed instructors and teaching assistants to view students' class participation details, examination results and an at-risk indicator. Based on their assessment results, students were sent personalised emails which included a list of resources to work on in their tutor centre. Using descriptive statistics and t -tests they found a significant difference between those who attended and those who did not attend the tutor centre. Following the use of prediction modelling, Corrigan et al. (2015) sent emails to students which included support details and a module position indicator. Dawson et al. (2017) identified at-risk students in seventeen modules, including STEM modules. In order to increase retention rates, trained personnel telephoned the at-risk students and detailed the available supports. They investigated the impact of this through χ^2 tests, logistic regression and mixed-effects modelling. Initially, the intervention appeared to have caused a significant increase in retention but after further rigorous evaluation this was proved untrue. As this is a relatively

new area, the ‘Refine’ step of the learning analytics cycle (Campbell & Oblinger, 2007) is under-researched, and the potential for university mathematics modules has not fully been explored.

MODULE AND METHOD

Practical Statistics is an introductory online statistics module for approximately 150 students, offered each semester in University College Dublin. Over the 12-week teaching semester, there are no face-to-face lectures, however, there are two one-hour face-to-face software laboratory lessons per week. The lecturer has taught *Practical Statistics* for five years with little change to the module content for the duration of this study. The only exception to this occurred in semester 2 of 2015/16 when a colleague taught *Practical Statistics*, although they covered the same content and used the same format as previous iterations. *Practical Statistics*’ continuous assessment contributes 40% to a student’s final module mark with the remaining 60% based on an end-of-semester 2-hour written examination. The continuous assessment consists of: accessed videos (2%); weekly lecture questions (6%); weekly Minitab laboratory tutorials (3%); a Minitab examination (10%); weekly R laboratory tutorials (4%); and an R examination (15%). In both semesters of 2017/18, the university closed for a few days owing to severe weather conditions. This resulted in the cancellation of the Minitab examination and a re-weighting of the continuous assessment components. For our statistical analysis, we focus on written examination marks rather than final module mark as these represent 60% of the final module mark for all students for every semester of this study. Unlike semester 1, in semester 2 there is a two-week midterm break for students between weeks 7 and 8 of the teaching semester.

Data Collection

Since 2015/16, we have collected: students’ demographic data, continuous assessment and examination marks; LMS log files; and, students’ MSC attendance. The LMS resources (for example online videos and lectures slides) are divided into fifteen folders based on the week which the material content relates to (week 1 module material, ..., week 12 module material, lecture questions solutions, module information, and past examination questions). We collated the data for each student under a pseudo number. In accordance with our ethics permission from the university ethics committee, students were provided with information sheets outlining the nature of this study and provided with the option of having their data removed from the study. However, no student withdrew.

In semester 1 of 2015/16, we conducted an online survey of *Practical Statistics*’ students aimed at understanding students’ resource usage, to which approximately 30% responded ($n = 38$). We analysed the responses to this survey and incorporated this information into the advice of our intervention email for future years. When asked about resource usage, students reported predominantly using resources provided by the lecturer, with external resources including Khan academy videos and *How to Lie with Statistics* by Huff. When asked about online learning, students’ responses were mixed with some students praising the flexibility of online learning and others finding it difficult to adjust to the freedom accompanying it.

However, students noted that the weekly lecture questions helped them to regulate their learning.

The Interventions

The aim of each of our interventions was to improve students’ academic achievement through encouraging engagement with module resources and reflection on prior material. This research is considered quasi-experimental as students receive an intervention based on a set-criteria rather than random assignment (see Table 1). For our initial intervention, in semester 1 of 2016/17, we emailed students of Practical Statistics at the beginning of weeks 6-7. Previous research (Howard, Meehan, & Parnell, 2018) identified weeks 5-6 as an “optimal time” to provide support to students and obtain a sufficient level of prediction accuracy. While the core information provided to all students in the email was the same, the email was phrased slightly differently depending on the tertile of students’ continuous assessment to-date. The email included the distribution of continuous assessment to-date (to allow students to compare their own continuous assessment mark to their peers) and following from the survey, study suggestions included: visiting statistics tutors in the MSC for free one-to-one tutoring; external resource recommendations (based on results of the survey distributed in 2015/16); suggestion of studying at the same times every week; and, a suggestion to study with friends in the university active learning environment rooms.

Table 1: Interventions provided to students by year and semester. The control group were identified retrospectively as at risk by using the criteria that their predicted module mark was less than 50.

Year	2015/16		2016/17		2017/18	
Semester	S1	S2	S1	S2	S1	S2
Email with advice and continuous assessment graphs	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	No
Email with advice and predicted mark	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
At-risk students receive weekly MSC emails	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
At-risk students invited to meet lecturer	No	No	No	No	No	Yes
Number of students in study	139	115	148	158	152	164
Criteria for at-risk students	Control Group	Control Group	Lowest Third	Predicted Mark <60	Predicted Mark <50	Predicted Mark <50
Number of at-risk students	37	19	47	38	30	26

From our initial exploratory analysis of the effectiveness of the email intervention, we found that it had no measurable impact upon students’ final examination mark. Therefore, in subsequent semesters, we escalated our interventions and/or changed our criteria for an at-risk student (Table 1). From semester 2 of 2016/17 onwards, at-risk students were identified using a prediction model, Bayesian Additive Regression Trees (Chipman, George, & McCulloch, 2010), and this was based on their LMS interactions, continuous assessment and demographic data. In semester 2 of 2016/17 the intervention remained the same. Starting in semester 1 of

2017/18, for our intervention escalation, rather than providing students with the distribution of the module's continuous assessment, at weeks 6-7 we provided them with their predicted module mark, and a disclaimer that this was not their final module mark. We emphasised that the predicted mark could be changed by studying. The MSC manager agreed to send weekly emails to students from week 7 who were identified as at-risk. These emails informed the students that their lecturer recommended they attend the MSC for additional support. However, this intervention had no effect in semester 1 of 2017/18. For semester 2 of 2017/18, in addition to the MSC emails, 26 at-risk students were emailed by the lecturer of the module, offering them a one-to-one meeting to discuss issues and/or their study plans for the remainder of the semester in relation to *Practical Statistics*. Upon receiving only three replies, the lecturer tried to phone the remaining 23 students. Several students had not provided correct contact details on the university system. Of the 26 students, the lecturer arranged meetings with 12 of them.

Evaluation of the Interventions

To analyse whether the interventions had a behavioural or/and academic impact on students, the final written examination marks, LMS usage and MSC attendance of students are compared over multiple offerings of the module while controlling for at-risk students. LMS and MSC are used as proxies for engagement. We acknowledge that engagement is complex and these proxies do not consider the quality of time spent on learning. In the case of LMS data, smoothed daily LMS activity with 95% confidence intervals are used for comparisons. Examination marks are compared using descriptive statistics (boxplots), analysis of variance (ANOVA) tests and linear regression. In addition, the level of MSC attendance is compared over multiple semesters. Survey responses suggested that some students had difficulty adjusting to and motivating themselves to engage with online modules. Following from the advice given to students to study at the same times each week, we examined whether there was a relationship between the dominant periodicity of students' resource usage and written examination marks using spectral analysis.

RESULTS: MEASURING THE IMPACT OF THE INTERVENTIONS

To allow for comparisons between at-risk students, we retrospectively identified students at-risk for 2015/16 using a prediction mark cut-off of 50% and Bayesian Additive Regression Trees. In Figure 1, we visually compare *Practical Statistics*' smoothed daily LMS activity for semester 1 and written examination marks over three years (similarly this can be done for semester 2). These comparisons are shown for the at-risk and not at-risk cohorts. The initial increase in LMS activity correlates with the first major continuous assessment, the Minitab examination in Week 6. The second increase in week 12 correlates with the second main continuous assessment, the R examination. Consistently the at-risk students had lower LMS activity. However, for semester 1 2017/18, the LMS activity for both student cohorts are

nearly perfectly aligned. This cannot be associated with the intervention as this alignment in LMS activity occurs both pre- and post-intervention.

Figure SEQ Figure * ARABIC 1: Daily LMS activity combined with boxplot of written examination marks for semester one factorised by whether students were identified as at-risk or not. The dashed line in a panel represents the date on which the initial intervention of that semester occurred.

Hypothesis testing is a popular method of analysing whether learning interventions have been effective. The ANOVA test is used for multiple mean comparisons. One of the assumptions of an ANOVA test is homogeneity of variances. To confirm whether the data follows this assumption, Bartlett’s test was used. Bartlett’s test was significant, which indicates that the assumption of equal variances is violated, and should be accounted for when using ANOVA. Using Welch’s ANOVA, to take into account the variance, we found no statistical difference in semester 1. For semester 2 a significant result was found with an F-value of 23.984 (p-value < 0.01, $\nu = 2$). We also used linear regression to investigate whether the year of intervention impacted at-risk students’ written examination mark as the intervention is escalated over the course of the study. For at-risk students, the year of intervention is not a significant explanatory variable. In our opinion, these changes in the distribution of marks do not provide sufficient evidence to endorse a positive impact of the learning analytics interventions. Rather the changes could have been caused by natural fluctuations having occurred owing to differences in student cohorts, end-of-semester examination paper et cetera.

The university has a free drop-in MSC for students taking mathematics/statistics modules. The MSC maintains detailed recordings of students visits to the centre. In recent years, the number of visits from *Practical Statistics*’ students has remained low (Table 2) despite the strong encouragement given to students to attend the MSC through the lecturer-student meetings.

Table 2: Number of Maths Support Centre visits for *Practical Statistics*.

Year	2015/16		2016/17		2017/18	
Semester	S1	S2	S1	S2	S1	S2
Total number of visits from students	20	2	20	7	16	12
Number of visits from at-risk students	2	0	2	1	0	2

One of the suggestions given to *Practical Statistics*' students, was that "students new to learning online have found that setting specific times every week to complete online material is beneficial". The hypothesis being that there is a relationship between the dominant periodicity of students' resource usage and written examination marks. From analysing time series plots of students' engagement with online resources, there was evidence of students consistently studying pre- and post-receipt of the intervention email; in other words, the email itself did not have an effect on the consistency of students' study patterns. To investigate whether adhering to a regular pattern benefited students, we used spectral analysis on the semester 2 2017/18 cohort. We chose this cohort as they were exposed to the final escalation of the intervention. Spectral analysis is the decomposition of a time series into underlying sine and cosine functions of different frequencies (Hill & Lewicki, 2006). This allows for the isolation of strong or important frequencies. We included a taper effect of 0.2 to reduce the importance of the beginning and end of our LMS activity series. Following from this, we identified each student's dominant periodicity of their study (the number of days for one full cycle of study). Unsurprisingly, the majority of students had a dominant study pattern which is less than seven days. We considered and found no relation between the dominant study cycle of students and their examination marks received. Upon closer examination, only 19% of the dominant periodicities were statistically significant (based on a p -value of 0.05).

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Learning analytics are not always implemented smoothly or without adaptation; as we have progressed in our longitudinal study, we have changed the at-risk criteria to focus our efforts, escalated the intervention implemented and altered the continuous assessment breakdown owing to university closures. This is a limitation in terms of the statistical analysis. However, it can be a beneficial effect of longitudinal studies since the key focus is to support students. In our study, we compared students' academic results, LMS data and MSC attendance. We also investigated students' dominant study patterns. While some studies use a stringent approach of a control versus an experiment group, ethically this can be harder to achieve in an education setting. We do not believe our interventions had a significant impact upon students' behaviour but rather this study emphasises the debate around the non-engagement of at-risk students. This idea of at-risk students failing to pursue help is not a new topic to education but more research is needed into encouraging engagement in at-risk students. This may involve investigating whether there is a stigma attached to accessing specific student supports, for example the MSC, or, whether students are unable to access supports owing to work or caring duties.

Na and Tasir (2017, p. 65) explain that "different at-risk students have different learning problems and, thus, different interventions are required". In our study, we escalated the intervention in a module, however we did not consider interventions on a global scale - whether the students' problems related to all statistics (or mathematics) modules or were across their programme. Problems could be caused by personal reasons and not necessarily owing to students' non-engagement. From the twelve face-to-face meetings between the lecturer and students, it became apparent that students were at-risk for a range of reasons.

Each student's case was unique, and this emphasises the need for a broader range of interventions as well as the inclusion of pastoral academic support. We concur with Na and Tasir (2017) that different at-risk students require different interventions, however, we propose approaching this by firstly identifying whether the required intervention should be targeted towards a specific module or should support the student across their programme. We hypothesise that at-risk students are more likely to have difficulties at the programme level whereas module-level interventions are more likely to resonate with the "average" student. Alternatively, Choi et al., (2018) conjecture that at-risk students may have metacognitive skills which constrain their ability to benefit from reflective learning analytics interventions. In Atif, Richard and Bilgin's (2015) examination of students' perceptions of learning analytics, factors affecting students' success included personal responsibilities, daily travel, work commitments, financial issues and emotional and physical health issues, with a limited number suggesting module-level factors of under-preparedness and support. Future work will investigate programme-level interventions. This includes pastoral support, for example peer-to-peer mentoring, meetings between students and student advisors, and campaigns to raise awareness of the university supports available.

REFERENCES

- Atif, A., Richards, D., & Bilgin, A. (2015). Student preferences and attitudes to the use of early alerts. In T. Bandyopadhyay, D. Beyene, & S. Negash (Eds.), *Americas Conference on Information Systems*, AMCIS 2015 (pp. 1-14). Puerto Rico: AMCIS.
- Cai, Q., Lewis, C. L., & Higdon, J. (2015). Developing an early-alert system to promote student visits to tutor centre. *Learning Assistance Review*, 20(1), 61-72.
- Campbell, J. P., & Oblinger, D. G. (2007). *Academic analytics*. Educause. Retrieved from <https://www.educause.edu/ir/library/pdf/PUB6101.pdf>.
- Chipman, H. A., George, E. I., & McCulloch, R. E. (2010). BART: Bayesian additive regression trees. *The Annals of Applied Statistics*, 4(1), 266-298.
- Choi, S. P. M., Lam, S. S., Li, K. C., & Wong, B. T. M. (2018). Learning analytics at low cost: At-risk student prediction with clicker data and systematic proactive interventions. *Educational Technology & Society*, 21(2), 273-290.
- Corrigan, O., Smeaton, A. F., Glynn, M., & Smyth, S. (2015). Using educational analytics to improve test performance. In G. Conole, T. Klobučar, C. Rensing, J. Konert, & E. Lavoué (Eds.), *Proceedings of Design for Teaching and Learning in a Networked World, 10th European Conference on Technology Enhanced Learning* (pp. 42-55). Toledo: Springer.
- Dawson, S., Jovanovic, J., Gašević, D., & Pardo, A. (2017). From prediction to impact: Evaluation of a learning analytics retention program. In *Proceedings of the 7th International Learning Analytics and Knowledge Conference* (pp. 474-478). New York, USA: ACM.
- Howard, E., Meehan, M., & Parnell, A. (2018). Contrasting prediction methods for early warning systems at undergraduate level. *The Internet and Higher Education*, 37(1), 66-75.
- Na, K. S., & Tasir, Z. (2017). A systematic review of learning analytics intervention contributing to student success in online learning. In *2017 International Conference on Learning and Teaching in Computing and Engineering (LaTICE)* (pp. 62-68). Retrieved from <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8064433>.